

Effect of drying temperature and time on Gesho leaf major beer brewing components

Author Details: Ayalew Demissew

Amhara Regional Agricultural Research Institute
Bahir Dar Food Science and Postharvest Handling Research Center
Po.box 794,

Abstract: Beer is typically brewed from four basic ingredients (water, a starch source, brewer's yeast and flavoring agent such as hops). In Ethiopian case hops are costly ingredient of beer which is imported with hard currency of the country. But this flavoring agent (hops) in beer production can also be substituted by locally available flavouring agent called gesho "Rhamnus Prinoide" leaf. In this study the effect of drying temperature and time on brewing components of gesho "Rhamnus Prinoide" leaf was examined using oven dryer. Brewing components of gesho "Rhamnus Prinoide" leaf were compared by taking the commercial hop brewing component as a standard. Drying temperature and time have a significant effect ($P < 0.05$) on major beer brewing components (Resin, Hop oil and Polyphenol) of gesho leaf. Not only drying temperature and time but also the interaction effect has significant effect on these major brewing components of the leaf. The optimal drying temperature and time of gesho leaf was also determined to commercialize the gesho leaf powder or pellet as hop substitute in commercial beer brewers as flavouring agent.

Key words: Gesho, Hop, Hop oil, Polyphenol and Resin

1. Introduction

Beer is not the only widely consumed alcoholic beverage in the world but also the third most popular drink after water and tea. Beer is mainly brewed from four basic ingredients which are water, a starch source, brewer's yeast, and a flavoring agent such as hops. Different types of beer are available in the market where this typicality comes from these ingredients, the additives used and the brewing processes. Beer is composed of a complex mixture of phenolic compounds extracted from the starch source and hop. Now a day's special trend from micro-breweries in the U.S.A. is the production of several range of extremely bitter beer created by the addition of extra hop during the brewing process. The hop derived xanthohumol and the iso-alpha acid are primarily responsible for the perceived bitterness of beer. Most of the secondary metabolites are not only important for health benefits; it is also needed for beer flavor as well as stability. But some secondary metabolites of beer will make it quality loss during storage by the creation of haze [1]. Beer contains nutrients such as carbohydrates, amino acids, minerals, and vitamins. In addition to nutrients beer also contains many of non-nutrient components including phenolic compounds. The type and quality of beer brewed depends the following factors, the variety of barley, the malting process, temperature and pH of mashing, sparging, wort boiling, the variety of hops added during wort boiling, and fermentation process. It has been estimated that about 70–80% of beer polyphenols are malt-derived. Barley polyphenols are changed in the malting and brewing process. The phenols found in malt are less characterized when compared to the phenol derived from hops. The phenols extracted from malt during mashing and sparging known as polyphenol or tannins and it also react with proteins in the wort to form chill haze or permanent haze. In order to control these problem reduce sparge temperature below 77°C; reduce sparge time and the alkalinity of brewing liquor [2]. The hop is a perennial climbing plant; the aerial part dies off in the autumn but the rootstock stays in the soil, sometimes for many years. The plant needs a support up which to grow. In the wild, hops are found in hedgerows but for cultivation they are trained up strings attached to permanent wirework. Hops are used in beer production in small amount to impart its characteristic aroma and bitterness. Hops also contribute to the beer its antifungal and antibiotic properties so that the produced beer remains safe during storage [3]. The composition of the hops is extremely important for the quality of the beer produced from it and on dry weight basis the bitter

substances (Resin) (18.5%), hop oil (0.5%), polyphenols (3.5%), protein (20.0%) and minerals (8.0%). The rest consists of cellulose and other materials which are unimportant for beer production. The most important components of hop for the production of beer are the bitter substances (resins) and essential oils or the hop oils [4]. During drying of hop the air speed and temperature should be carefully controlled so that volatile compounds which are heat sensitive will not be destroyed with increasing air temperature for prolonged time. But if the air speed is too low, the air will become saturated with moisture in the lower layers of the bed where lastly deposit moisture on the hops in the upper layer which finally causes discoloration of the hops [3]. *Gesho* is a plant which grows up to six meters and it is cultivated in Ethiopia for its importance in the production of domestically fermented beverages like *tella* and *teji*. In Ethiopia the leaves and stems of *gesho* are crucial components in the production of traditional fermented beverages [5]. Although *gesheo* leaf had been used as flavouring as well as antibiotic agent in traditional beverages, it had yet tried to commercialize it as hop substitute in commercial beer brewing industries. In doing so drying is the critical process in *gesho* leaf powder or pellet production. Because major brewing components of *gesho* leaf powder are volatile compounds which will be destroyed during drying by high temperature and moisture. Traditionally *gesho* leaf is dried simply using sunlight by spreading the leaf on the ground that had been already prepared for drying purpose where it negatively effect on its taste and flavor. In this study the optimal drying temperature and time had been investigated and hence it can potentially substitute the commercial hop imported as a flavouring agent in commercial beer brewing industries. So *gesho* leaf powder or pellet dried at the optimal drying condition had similar brewing components as that of the commercial hop imported by Dashen brewery Share Company.

1.1. The general objective of this study

Determination of optimum drying conditions of *gesho* leaf powder as commercial hop substitute in modern beer brewing industries

1.2. Specific objectives

1.2.1. To determine the optimum drying temperature of *gesho* leaf as hop substitute in commercial beer brewing industries

1.2.2. To determine the optimum drying time of *gesho* leaf as hop substitute in commercial beer brewing industries

1.2.3. To characterize the composition of dried *gesho* leaf for its major brewing components as hop substitute in commercial beer brewing industries

2. Material and Method

2.1. Sample collection and preparation

Gesho leaf which was physiologically matured collected from Amhara Agriculture Research Institute (ARARI) at Adet Agriculture Research Center. The collected *gesho* leaf sample was cleaned manually to remove seed and other extraneous materials such as stalks and dusts before drying process conducted.

2.2. Gesho leaf drying

Drying of *gesho* leaf was conducted by drying oven to investigate the effect of drying factors (drying temperature and time) on the quality of *gesho* leaf powder as commercial hop substitute in commercial beer brewing industries. During conducting the experiment, the sample was dried at different temperature and time with five levels (40°C, 45°C, 50°C, 55°C and 60°C) and (1hr, 1.5hr, 2hr, 2.5hr and 3hr) to investigate the optimum drying parameters of drying process. Then dried *gesho* leaf was milled using laboratory grain miller at Amhara Agricultural Research Institute grain laboratory and packed with polyethylene using bag seller. Finally products were characterized for its important brewing components (polyphenol, resin and hop oil).

2.2.1. Characterization of major beer brewing components Gesho leaf

2.2.1.1. Polyphenol content

Polyphenol were determined by the modified vanillin assay method. 200 mg samples were weighed and then extracted with 10 ml absolute methanol for 20 minutes rotating screw cap culture tubes (130*100mm). The mixture then is centrifuged for 10minutes at 3000*G and the supernatant were used in the analysis. About 0.0 –

1.0 ml aliquot of catechin standard is dispensed into two sets of culture tubes and each sample was brought to 1.0 ml by the addition of absolute methanol. Incubate the tubes in water bath. 5 ml of the working vanillin reagent was added at 1 min interval to one set of standards, and 5ml of the 4% HCl solution is added at 1 min interval to the second set of standards. After 20 min, the absorbance of sample solution and the standard solution were measured at 500 nm by using spectrophotometer. The absorbance of the blank is subtracted from the absorbance of the corresponding vanillin-contain sample. A standard curve has been constructed (Absorbance vs Catechin) and the linear portion of the curve will be extrapolated to produce the standard curve. Finally, the polyphenol contents will be calculated. Values of tannins will be expressed in milligram of D-catechin equivalent per gram of sample.

Polyphenol in mg/100g = (absorbance density*weight of sample *100) -----equation (1)

$$\% \text{ Polyphenol} = \frac{P_w}{W_s} * 100 \dots \dots \dots \text{equation (1.1)}$$

Where:

P_w -Weight of polyphenol in gm

W_s -Weight of sample in gm (100gm)

2.2.1.2. Resin content

2.2.1.2.1. Total resin content

For resin analysis 20g of the sample was dissolved in 100 ml of cold methanol in a conical bottom flask and the mixture was vigorously agitated by swirling the flask. Thereafter, the solution was filtered. The filtrate containing the resin was then dried and the total resin was calculated as a percentage of the original sample weight.

$$\text{Resin (\%)} = \frac{M_{df}}{M_{initial}} * 100 \dots \dots \dots \text{equation (2)}$$

Where: M_{df} and $M_{initial}$ are weight of extract after dry and initial weight of the sample respectively

2.2.1.2.2. Soft and hard resin content

With regard to resin determination, 20 grams of each sample was dissolved in 20 ml of n-hexane thoroughly stirred and filtered using filter paper. Filtrate was dried to a constant weight at 50 degree centigrade. The soft resin was calculated as the percentage of the original weight of sample dissolved in the n-hexane. Hard resin was determined by subtracting soft resin from total resin.

$$\% \text{ soft resin} = \frac{M_{final}}{M_{initial}} * 100 \dots \dots \dots \text{equation (3)}$$

Where:

M_{final} = weight of the final dried sample

$M_{initial}$ = Weight of the sample dissolved in the n-hexane

2.2.2. Hop oil content

In hop oil content analysis, 10 gram of the sample was taken in 1000 ml round bottom flask and then 750 ml of distilled water was added. The mixture was agitated by swirling the flask. A Clevenger apparatus was mounted and fitted on to the round bottom flask and then connected to a tap water source. The set up was held tight with a retort stand and the mixture was placed on a suitable electric heating mantle. When the water boils, the steam rises through the stockings, thus extracting the essential oil. The delivery from the condenser was connected to the separating funnel to receive the mixture of steam and oil on condensation. After 120 min, the set up was switched-off and allowed to cool. The water-oil mixture was decanted to separate the oil from the water at the water oil interface. After drying in an electric oven the mass was recorded and calculated as a percentage from the original sample.

$$\% \text{ hop oil} = \frac{M_{df}}{M_{initial}} * 100 \dots \dots \dots \text{equation (4)}$$

Where:

M_{df} = weight of the sample after drying phenomenon

$M_{initial}$ = Initial weight of the sample

2.2.3. Data analysis

Chemical and physical measurements were statically analyzed by design expert-7 software. The comparison between sample treatments and the indices were done by using analysis of variance with a probability ($P < 0.05$). In this experimental work all physical and chemical measurements were performed in triplicates.

3. Result and discussion

3.1. Effect of drying temperature and time on resin content

From figure-one below (drying temperature and time interaction effect graph) the concentration of resin is high in a drying temperature range from 40°C to 50°C within the time interval of 1 to 2 hours. Although the concentration of resin was high at those drying operating conditions, it couldn't be recommend as point of optimal processing condition because the moisture content of the product was also high which leads to the deterioration of resin by the action of oxygen as it had been stated in [4]. Then the product would have inferior quality which finally makes it to be less demanded in the market for commercial beer brewing industries as hop substitute flavouring agent.

On the other side drying temperature greater than 55°C and time more than 2hrs indicate low amount of resin as a result of high temperature break down of α -acids which also makes inferior quality. At optimal drying temperature and time (55°C for 2hrs) the product had 18.015 percent which meets the standard of commercial hop set by American trade association.

- Temperature in °C, Time in hr and resin (%) in dry weight basis

Figure-1: Effect of temperature and time interaction on resin content

3.2. Effect of drying temperature and time on hop oil content

In Figure-two below the hop oil content in *gesho* leaf powder decreases at drying temperature greater than 55°C and time greater than 2hrs. At these temperatures range the decrement of hop oil was due the action of high temperature destruction. But the hop oil content was high when the *gesho* leaf was dried at temperature range from 40°C to 55°C for a given time interval where the moisture content is above the recommended. At the

optimal drying temperature and time (55°C for 2hrs), the product would have hop oil content of 0.98 percent on dry weight basis where the product meets the desired amount to substitute commercial hop in commercial beer brewing industries in relation to essential oil content.

- Temperature in °C, Time in hr and hop oil (%) in dry weight basis
- Figure-2: Effect of temperature and time interaction on hop oil content

3.3. Effect of drying temperature and time on polyphenol content

As it is shown in the figure-three below the polyphenol content of the *gesho* leaf powder was found higher at a drying temperature range 40 to 50°C for nearly all drying time ranges (from 1 to 3hr) but for a temperature range greater than 55°C the polyphenol content decreases. The cause of polyphenol content to decrease in a drying temperature greater than 55°C was due the action of high heat on these semi-volatile components of *gesho* leaf. At the optimal drying condition (55°C for 2hrs) *gesho* leaf had polyphenol content 3.53% which is equal as that of commercial hop stated [4].

- Temperature in °C, Time in hr and polyphenol (%) in dry weight basis
- Figure-3: Effect of temperature and time interaction on polyphenol content

4. Conclusion

The optimal drying condition (drying temperature and time) for the production of *Gesho* leaf powder or pellet as hop substitute in commercial beer brewing industry was found to be 55°C for two hours. At the optima drying

condition the bitterness substances, the hop oil and polyphenol content of *Gesho* leaf which are highly heat sensitive were found 18.025, 0.96% and 3.53%. These major brewing components of *Gesho* leaf was also reported by [7], although the researcher analyzes the fresh leaf. As a conclusion at the optimal drying condition *Gesho* leaf can certainly substitute the imported commercial hop for commercial beer brewing industries in terms of beer brewing components. The finding also helps in saving foreign currency by import substitution of the commercial hop. Commercializing this flavoring agent as hop substitute improved the livelihood of farmer's especially rural women where the cultivation was mainly held by women in Ethiopia. The finding also would reduce the coast of commercial beer brewing process so that it will increase the profitability of beer brewers.

5. Recommendation

Evaluation of optimally dried *Gesho* leaf powder needs further study in commercial beer production by substituting the commercial hop. The impact of soil type and growing environment on composition of brewing component of *Gesho* leaf shall also need further investigation.

6. Reference

- i. Madsen, E.S., Wu, Y., *Marketing and Globalization of the Brewing Industry*, in: Cabras, I., Higgins, D., Preece, D. (Eds.), *Brewing, Beer and Pubs*. Palgrave Macmillan UK, London, pp. 34–60, 2016.
- ii. De Cooman, L., Aerts, G., Overmeire, H., *Alteration of the Profiles of Iso-Alpha-Acids During Beer Ageing Marked Instability of Trans-Iso-Alpha-Acids and Implication for Beer Bitterness, Consistency in Relation to Tetrahydroiso-Alpha-Acids*. *Journal of institute of brewing*, 106, 2000, 169–178.
- iii. Versele, M. and De Keukeleire, D., *Chemistry and analysis of hop and beer bitter acids*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1991.
- iv. Kunze, W., *Technology of Brewing and Malting*. 7th Edn. VLB Berlin, Germany, 1996.
- v. Ashenafi, M., *A review on the microbiology of indigenous fermented foods and beverages of Ethiopia*. *Ethiopian journal biological sciences*, 5(2), 2006, 189-245.
- vi. Berhanu A., *Microbial profile of Tella and the role of gesho (Rhamnus prinoides) as bittering and antimicrobial agent in traditional Tella (Beer) production*. *Journal internation food research* 21(1), 2013, 23-35.